

Barcelona Supercomputing Center 2021

Women Leaders BSC Bioinfo4Women Programme

01 INTRODUCTION

On October 8th, and within the framework of the inauguration of the BSC-Repsol building, the B4W program developed an activity to give voice and visibility to BSC personnel, in particular its women researchers and technicians.

The proposed activity had the general purpose of connecting the BSC staff with women leaders in different fields of research, business, politics, among others, in order to change the existing perspective and perception towards the women leaders, learn from them how they have developed their professional career, providing references to the researchers of the center.

As an additional purpose, it was intended to connect the BSC staff with the idea of creating a community, making the B4W program known internally, and collecting their concerns in reference to the development of the professional career of women or other issues of their interest.

Event participants

Women Leaders: Victòria Alsina, Karina Gibert, Gemma Lienas, Carme Valls, Núria Vergés, Elizabeth Zapata.

- **Victòria Alsina**, Minister of Foreign Action and Open Government, Government of Catalonia. tbc
- **Karina Gibert**, Full Professor at UPC, coFounder and member of the board at IDEAI-UPC, Vicepresident of Equity and Ethics at COEINF.
- **Gemma Lienas**, Member of the Catalan Parliament for equality and feminism.
- **Carme Valls**, Politician and physician specialized in endocrinology with a gender perspective. Director of the "Women, Health and Quality of Life" program at the Center for Health Analysis and Programs CAPS.
- **Núria Vergés**, Directorate General of Care, Organization of Time and Equity at Work.
- **Elisabeth Zapata**, Distinguished Technologist at HP.

BSC participants

The invitation was sent from the Communication department to all BSC staff. The participants by department in the event were: Life Sciences (15), Earth Sciences (7), Computer Sciences (2), CASE (2), PMO (3), Administration (1). In total, 28 women and 2 men participated.

02 DEVELOPMENT

1. Atmosphere

All the tables participated very actively, both listening and speaking, in a very relaxed and friendly tone. An open, relaxed and stimulating atmosphere was created in all the tables, where all the participants at the table dared to speak, ask questions and express opinions. It should be noted that male BSC researchers also participated in the event, the activity was open to all staff. Informal conversations were created that gave way to commenting on personal situations and asking questions of the guest that would probably have been avoided in another context.

2. Temes de conversació

The topics of conversation differed a lot between the different tables, which greatly enriches the experience and allows us to broaden the spectrum of topics that concern the researchers. In summary, the following topics were discussed:

- The importance of including the gender and sex perspective in data analysis and scientific projects and the need to include it in grants for the financing of science.
- Scientific conditioning subject to political interests, and research conditioning through funding.
- Job opportunities beyond the academic path, the possibilities for professional development in the public environment, the existing possibilities, the hiring problems and the professional career prospects.
- Motherhood and its consequences in the workplace, as a loss of opportunities to progress with many more consequences for women than for men, specifically in the scientific environment (when maximum productivity and critical points to climb the job tend to coincide around the optimal age for having children).
- The need to include and involve men in activities and debates, they consider themselves generally excluded from the topic and think they have a lot to contribute.

- Situation in the workplace of the BSC, particularly women, and the presence of women in the world of engineering.
- The need to have leading and inspiring women scientists and technologists.
- The existing prejudices towards women in technical careers and the need to create and build a support network to face them, together with tools to overcome the sexist situations that can be encountered. Lack of knowledge about existing channels to report abuse / discrimination and the decision that is made many times (as highlighted in the stories): "go, for what I have left, I can put up with it, I get my doctorate and I'm going." Unfortunately, this situation is repeated in the scientific field due to the lack of support tools, which perpetuates unacceptable behaviors.
- Obstacles in the development of a scientific career such as the established need of having to go abroad if you want to establish yourself as a researcher later in Spain. Is it really necessary?
- The constant need for professional women to have to demonstrate their aptitude to belong to departments such as engineering, physics etc. How at work basic concepts are unnecessarily explained to women who are experts in them, assuming their ignorance.
- The excess of tasks assigned to women normally related to the organization of social activities such as a meal, a group outing, making an itinerary of material that the group needs, etc. for the fact of being women.
- The extension and inclusion of the feminist collective within other groups.

03 PROPOSALS

During the conversation at the different tables, many interesting proposals were suggested:

- To have a library on gender perspective at the BSC open to all employees and with books available throughout a loan system. In the same way, anyone who could contribute to this library with donations.

- The participants have shown a particular interest to continue with this activity, to learn more about the debate topics share the comments and the advisable conclusions at the different tables. Participants in the activity want to be included in the discussions to be able to escort and understand the donation's perspective, as well as expressing their own points of view.

04 FINAL CONCLUSION

All the participants, including the women leaders, left the activity very happy, which they defined as inspiring, profitable, interesting and **necessary**.

In general, the participants were short on time and left many issues and questions left untreated with the invited women, who also would have liked to be able to participate in more than one table. Additionally, the researchers mentioned that it would be positive to have more exchange spaces within the BSC staff to get to know each other, generate synergies and promote research collaborations.

The importance of talking to women with more experience who can provide a different vision, as well as the possibility of meeting and dialoguing with other BSC women, has been highlighted, since it can hardly be done in other spaces / events.

There has been a general request to continue and repeat this type of activities at the BSC.

05 ANNEX: IMPACT ON SOCIAL NETWORKS¹

The activity was disseminated through the official channels of the program on Twitter and LinkedIn with the aim of communicating the activity once it was completed, giving relevance to the program and the BSC in the framework of the inauguration of the BSC-Repsol building, as well as encouraging the conversation between the women leaders and participants of the activity.

The [post](#) on the professional social network LinkedIn produced 3,720 impressions, with 99 reactions, 335 clicks. Some women leaders used this medium to acknowledge the invitation and highlight the positive experience of talking with our researchers.

¹ Data collected as of November 2nd 2021

In the case of the social network twitter, we carried out a [thread](#) in which we presented the activity and the women leaders, we highlighted the objective of the activity, we remembered the first edition of this activity during the 2019 AdvCompBio international conference and finally we showed the final photo with women leaders and participants of the closing of the activity. The thread got 13,348 impressions along with a total participation of 934. Women leaders and participants interacted with our tweets in addition to generating conversation among them in which they highlighted the usefulness of the activity, the opportunity to talk with relevant women, in addition to knowing and expanding their networks with other BSC researchers.

Simona Giardina
 @giardina_simona

Pasar una tarde con [#CarneValls](#), discutiendo sobre medicina con perspectiva de género. Una vez más, gracias [@Bioinfo4women](#) para organizar el "Meeting with Women Leaders" y darnos la oportunidad de conocer a mujeres tan especiales [@BSC_CNS](#)

Bioinfo4Women @Bioinfo4women · Oct 8
 Inspiring "Meeting with Women Leaders" event. 30 researchers have informal talks with:
 • @VictoriaAlsina
 • @GemmaLienas
 • @KarinagibertK
 • #CarneValls @Caps_RedCaps
 • @NuVerges
 • #ElizabethZapata @HP
 Org. by @Bioinfo4Women in the framework of the @BSC_CNS building opening.

8:43 PM · Oct 8, 2021 · Twitter for Android

8 Likes 1 Retweet

Bianca Mezzina
 @biancamzn

Thanks [@Bioinfo4women](#) for this initiative! 🥰 I had a very inspiring - and fun! - coffe with [@KarinagibertK](#) and got in touch with other colleagues from [@BSC_CNS](#) (so nice to meet you!). I hope there will be more... 😊

P.S. 10 points if you spot me in the pic

Bioinfo4Women @Bioinfo4women · Oct 8
 "Meeting with Women Leaders": inspiring talks by female role models and new contacts to strengthen our networks. Thanks to all women leaders @VictoriaAlsina @gemmallenas @KarinagibertK #CarneValls @NuVerges #ElizabethZapata and @BSC_CNS researchers and staff.

6:40 PM · Oct 8, 2021 · Twitter Web App

21 Likes 3 Retweets